

Gender Diversity and Environmental Reporting of Listed Manufacturing Firms in Nigeria

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Abstract

Global economic developments are usually characterized by environmental activities that result in problems such as growing pollution, global warming, deforestation, desertification, uncontrolled dumping of waste materials among others. These developments have increased the pressure on firms from stakeholders to disclose their efforts towards protecting the earth and its resources. In the light of these, the study examined the effect of gender diversity on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It has a population of 51 manufacturing firms and a sample of 31 firms which was arrived at based on a criterion that only listed manufacturing firms with full data over the period of the study (2009 – 2019) are considered. It used secondary sources of data gathering and data were extracted from content analysis of annual reports and accounts of listed manufacturing firms understudied. The data gathered were analyzed using multiple regression technique; also diagnostic test such as normality, multicollinearity, heteroskedasticity, and Hausman specification were conducted on the data used. The study found that gender diversity has significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Based on this finding, the study recommends that the proportion of female directors on board should be increased in order to significantly improve environmental reporting endeavour of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Keyword: ISO 14031 reporting guideline, Voluntary disclosure, Diagnostic test, Information asymmetry.

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1. Introduction

The idea of environmental reporting is vital on the awareness that societal resources should be preserved if at all, the pursuit of the global economic development and welfare is to be achieved. The environment must not be destroyed in the course of pursuing economic gain; and the use of its resources to pursue these economics gains by businesses must be optimized; but how well optimized can be reasonably ascertained by the impact which businesses have made on the society through environmental reporting. Environmental reporting involves release of information on the impact of organization's activities on the natural environment and such activities include, recycling, carbon management, emission and pollution management, tree planting and wild life conservation among others (Uyagu, 2019). The environmental information could be released through, annual reports, newsletter, press releases, magazines and sustainability reports.

The decision whether a firm engages in environmental reporting or not can be influenced by several board characteristics, such as gender diversity, board size, board independence, CEO duality, ownership concentration amongst others. However, this study focused on gender diversity in order to examine its effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Gender diversity is a component of board's decision-making tools that may affect either positively or negatively the level of environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. For example, Yaroson and Giwa (2016) opined that, the presence of female director on board would

lead to an increase in environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria and vice versa. In examining above statement, a board with female director may have the opportunity to make a robust decision, because of diversity of gender on board, which may result in more environmental activities being reported. Gender diversity can be described as the proportion of female directors to total members on board. The gender diversity of the board could affect the level of environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. According to Gao, Hervai and Xiao (2015), the presence of female directors on board is a crucial aspect of corporate governance that can affect the extent of reporting environmental activities.

There exist distinct problems with corporate environmental reporting, it is unfortunate that irrespective of corporate governance in place, manufacturing firms in Nigeria have left trail of woes in their path with so much damage and problems to human life in the environmental where they operate; such as air and water pollution, habitat destruction, land degradation among others. It suffices to know that air and water pollution has become a significant environmental problem in Nigeria as it emits 70 million metric tons of carbon dioxide annually (USEIA, 1999). This adversely affects the socio-economic activities of local communities like Niger Delta, which is primarily based on fishing and farming.

In Nigeria, environmental reporting seems to be at its lowest ebb, due to ineffectiveness of gender diversity (Liao, Luo & Tang, 2015). Also, in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, women on board are sometimes marginalized and discriminated upon when it comes to policy formulation and decision making in respect of corporate activities such as environmental issues (Mgbame & Onosaye, 2015). In addition, Nigeria being a developing and culturally biased nation, it is likely that women on board will not be vocal when it comes to decision on environmental issues. In other words, they can be marginalized and discriminated against. In addition, as regards environmental reporting, different organizations such as the chemical manufacturing association of Nigeria have issued guidelines, but these guidelines are only advisory in nature and not mandatory.

The previous studies concentrated on western economies (Aburaya, 2012; Akba, 2016; Barako & Brown, 2008; Campbell, 2004; Goyal, 2013), of which the findings and recommendations cannot be generalized to Nigeria because of the differences in economic system, market structure, geographical location and reporting requirements. In other to fill this gap, the study examines the effect of gender diversity on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms from Nigeria perspective, being a third world economy. The focus of the study is to assess the effect of gender diversity on reporting environmental activities of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. In order to achieve this, a hypothesis which says, gender diversity has no significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria was developed and tested. The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant literature; section 3 details the research methodology; section 4 presents the results and findings; and section 5 presents conclusion and recommendations.

2. Review Related Literature

This section is discussed under the following sub themes; conceptual review, review of empirical studies of effect of gender diversity on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria and finally theoretical review. The conceptual issues of this study are related to environmental reporting and gender diversity. Aburaya (2012) states that environmental reporting is a means of communicating the environmental information concerning the effect which

economic activities of an organisation may have on the environment. Also, Campel (2004) simply defines environmental reporting as the dissemination of the information pertaining to the impact an organizational process or operation may have on the natural environment to the stakeholders. It suffices that the contents of environmental reports are useful for stewardship, comparison and honesty, and such information can be reported through, press releases, newsletter, annual reports, Magazines and sustainability reports.

Corporate environmental reporting is justified on several grounds. An international study of environmental reporting in Europe, Japanese and North American companies found that the main reasons underlying the dissemination of corporate environmental information are sense of duty to the environment, public relations, competitive advantage and future legal requirements. Environmental reporting can be measured using the variables contained in International Standard Organization (ISO) 14031. It was established with the aim of providing voluntary standards that provides specific requirements and principles for environmental management and up to date, it is one of the most well known and widely used specification standards in environmental management and reporting (Uyagu, 2019).

Gender diversity is defined as the proportion of the female directors on the board (Liao, Luo & Tang, 2015). The concept of gender diversity is to diffuse board structure with female counterparts; being on the board like the male directors. The essence is to give equal opportunities or empowerment to the female folks. According to Modestus (2020), a survey carried out indicated that despite the ambition to attain a top-level in career, female professionals in the firms are largely constrained by inadequate opportunities relative to gender bias, unequal pay, harassment among others. It is likely that the inclusion of women in firms' board member confer positive image on the firm because, problems are better solved when board gender are adequately represented within the board, conveying positive signal to environmental report. Board gender diversity is necessary because, of the crucial role of female director who differ socially and ethically from male counterpart.

Gender diversity is imperative, because of increasing change in the dynamic of business worldwide; organizations such as listed manufacturing firms need an environment for all resources and talent to thrive irrespective of gender or experience. In addition, the presence of women on the board enhances the ability of the business to run healthily and therefore improve the disclosure of environmental issues in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

The different orientation that exists between female and male has made the inclusion of female directors on corporate board an element that can affect the extent of environmental reporting. Bernardi, Bean and Weippert (2005) affirmed that organizations with more women on boards were likely to embrace ethical values in corporate conduct. This means, women would not have incidence of attendance problems than male members, the punctuality of female directors to board meetings will serve as encouragement to male counterparts. More so, it will result in better board room decision and greater level of effectiveness in reporting environmental issues.

Rahman and Post (2012), assert that female directors pay more attention to social activities relating to donations, educational supports and aids to non-governmental institutions, rather than environmental issues. However, Gallen and Persuit (2017), assert that the presence of female director can improve decision making process and furnish better information with regards to environmental activities. This is possible because, female leaders exhibit peculiar positive

characteristics such as, innovation, proactiveness, transformational and are more conscious in excessive risk exposure which stand them out more than their male counterparts in strategic planning.

Liao, Luo and Tang (2014) assert that women have different role from men in society; therefore, female directors may take different approach to environmental matters. Victor and Fodio (2012) evaluate the effect of board characteristics on environmental reporting among listed companies in Nigeria. A sample of twenty-one environmentally sensitive firms was analyzed using logistic regression. The study covers a period of 5 (2005-2009) years. They find that gender diversity is a means of better monitoring of managers, because gender diversity increases board independence; that is, the more female directors on board the better they control on managers. Emmanuel, Uwuigbe, Teddy, Tolulope and Eytomi (2018) examined corporate diversity and corporate environmental reporting of listed manufacturing companies in Nigeria. The study considered both industrial and consumer goods firms, respectively. A sample of 17 firms out of 37 firms was selected for this study using purposive random sampling spanning the period 2012 – 2016. The finding from the study revealed that gender diversity significantly influenced corporate environmental reporting of listed firms. However, contrary to the suggestion, a gender diversity sensitive board may not necessarily lead to a better monitor of managers, because the desire to protect self-interest by the managers can scuttle or distract every attempt to monitor managers' activities through board gender diversity.

In addition, Post, Rahman and Rubon, (2011) investigated the effect of women on board using environmental report of 78 Malaysian firms. It was discovered that a board having a sizeable number of female directors has positive influence on environmental report. Ben-Amer, Change and McIlkenny, (2015) examined the impact of female representation on the board through environmental reporting. It was revealed that there was significant influence when there was increase in the number of female directors on board. The same result may not be obtained in Nigeria, because Canada and Nigeria are under different cultural, political and economic environment.

Yaroson and Giwa (2016), investigate the impact of gender diversity on environmental reporting of seven (7) conglomerates quoted on the Nigerian Stock Exchange for a period (2005-2014), multivariate regression was adopted to analyze the data. The finding shows that an increase in gender diversity leads to an increase in corporate environmental reporting of listed conglomerates in Nigeria. Therefore, an increase in gender diversity may lead to an improvement in board decisions concerning environmental issues in Nigeria listed manufacturing firms.

Barako and Brown (2008) examine the effect of board representation on corporate social reporting. The study period is 2005 – 2008 and 100 listed firms constitute the sample size. They find women on board have positive influence on the extent of disclosure related to environmental issues. In other words, an increase in the number of women on board increases reporting of environmental issues of listed firms.

In this study, control variable of firm size was used as done by (Aburaya, 2012; Uwuigbe, 2011; Uyagu, 2019). Aburaya (2012) considers firm size because, it is expected that the size of a firm will affects report on environmental issues in Nigeria listed non-financial firms. More so, bigger firms are more likely to be concerned with their corporate environmental reputation, since

they are more visible to external stakeholders who always demand for an improved environmental performance. Previous studies have explained the result in respect of size of a company and environmental reporting. Greek evidence shows that size is a strong determinant of environmental ratings (Galani, Gravas & Stavropoulos, 2012). Nigeria evidence shows that firm size is not significant on environmental disclosure (Uyagu, 2019). In the work of Ismail and Ibrahim (2008) using a sample of 60 companies in manufacturing sector, found a positive and significant influence of firm size on environmental reporting.

Different theoretical approaches have been used to explain environmental reporting of firms; such as agency theory, legitimacy theory, stakeholder's theory, political economy theory among others. However, for the purpose of this study, agency theory and legitimacy theory were considered. Agency theory has been variously used by researchers in an effort to explain the control put in place by the managers to alleviate a perceived information asymmetry. According to Aburaya (2012), an agency model alludes that due to information disproportionate and self-interest, stakeholders will seek to solve the problem by setting controls that will adjust the interest of managers to those of stakeholders in order to minimize the depth of information disproportionate and possible advantage for managers to advance their own interest.

In the context of environmental issues, the board directors, as an agent is concerned about developing good corporate environmental practices on behalf of their shareholders (principal). This is necessary in creating a good image for the firm to some investors with a view to convincing them to invest with the company. In addition, exhibiting pleasant corporate environmental conduct may increase the company's reputation, command public respect and boost the shareholders confidence in terms of the safety of their investment (Galani, Gravas, & Stavropoulos, 2012).

Legitimacy theory is defined as a situation in which a company's value system is in line with that of a larger society (Dowling & Pfeffer, 1975). When a difference occurs between the two value systems, this constitutes dangers to the organisation's legitimacy. The theory explains that companies continually seek to operate within the realm of the society. Therefore, in accepting the theory's idea, an organisation would freely report on activities like environmental, if it is perceived by management that those activities were anticipated by the society in which it functions (Deagan, 2002; Deegan Ranking & Voght, 2002; Cormier & Gordan, 2001). It suffices to know that legitimacy theory relies on the notion that there is a social contract between a company and the society in which it operates. The legitimacy theory argues that firms will offer information bordering around its activities to society including environmental information. According to O'Donovan (2004), this could better be done by using environmental reporting so as to gain a reputable image and acknowledgement by society. Also, companies need to be fair in their environmental dealings and therefore legitimacy theory provides disclosing approaches that organizations may apply to improve their existence in most possible best way.

Many empirical studies indicate that firms legitimize their activities because corporate management reacts to community expectations (Ashafoke & Ilaboya. 2017; DembNeubaur, 2018; Halil, 2016). The legitimate theory furnishes a complete view point in regard to environmental reporting, it explains that firms are compelled by the social contract to engage in socially desirable activities, which can sustain their continued survival.

From the foregoing theoretical reviews, the theory underpinning the study is agency theory, because, gender diversity is among board control mechanisms that can prevent conflicts that may arise between stakeholders and management, which agency theory tends to address. Therefore, the existence of effective gender diversity can promote adequate reporting of environmental issues, which in turn ameliorates the gap between the principal and agent.

3. Methodology

The study investigates gender diversity and environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The population is fifty-one (51) quoted firms in Nigeria, comprising three sectors; industrial, consumer and pharmaceutical, the members of the population that are not suitable for the study due to incomplete information or delisting on Nigerian stock exchange were eliminated by filters. The new population of the study is thirty one listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria and this will also serve as the sample size for the study.

This study sourced data from corporate annual reports of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. The choice of annual report arises because, they can readily be obtained and assessed from the selected quoted firms for the period 2009 – 2019. Multiple regression was run with the aid of STATA 16 for the purpose of analyzing the data.

Content analysis was used in gathering data and any of the sampled firms could garner maximum of 60 scores and minimum of 0. The reporting score was calculated thus:

$$RS = 60$$

$$\frac{\sum r_i}{1 = 1}$$

Where:

RS = Reporting Score

$r_i = 1$ if the item is disclosed and 0 if not.

$1 = 1, 2, 3 \dots 60$. A reported items are then summed up and divided by 60 to arrive at a value for the dependent variable. (Wiseman, 1982 & Uyagu, 2019)

The multiple regression analysis model was also adopted as previously used by (Aburaya, 2012; Eneyubo, 2013; Ofe & Ashinedu, 2019)

$$ER = f(GD, FS) \quad (1)$$

ER = (Environmental information, Employees and Safety Information and Community Development)

Model 1:

$$ENV1_{it} = a + \beta_1 GD_{it} + \beta_2 FS_{it} + \sum \dots \dots \dots 2$$

Model 2:

$$ES_{it} = a + \beta_1 GD_{it} + \beta_2 FS_{it} + \sum \dots \dots \dots 3$$

Model 3:

$$CD_{it} = a + \beta_1 GD_{it} + \beta_2 FS_{it} + \sum \dots \dots \dots 4$$

Whereas:

GD = Gender diversity

FS = Firm size

ENVI = Environmental information

- ES = Employees and safety information
 CD = Community development
 a = Constant
 β_1 = Model parameters or linear regression coefficients
 Σ = The error term used in the regression model
 i = Number of observations
 t = Time period.

The independent variable is Gender diversity, while the dependent variable is environmental reporting proxied by environmental disclosure index using International Standard Organization (ISO) 14031. The ISO 14031 contains five items with sixty (60) check list instruments subdivided into five categories of; environmental information, community development and others, energy, employees and safety and product safety. However, for the purpose of this study, environmental information, employees and safety information, and community development will be used to proxy environmental reporting. This is because they are environmental indices that attract the attention of management of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

The study contains control variable firm size (FS). This is because it is consistently found to be related to level and extent of reporting (Campell, 2004; Salama, 2017; Garcia & Larringa, (2003).

Table 1
Variable Definition and Measurement

Variables	Definitions	Measurement	Sources
Independent variables			
GD	Gender diversity	The proportion of female directors to total number of members on board at the year end.	Barako & Brown (2008) Rupley et al., (2012); Konrad et al., (2008)
Control variables			
FS	Firm size	Log of total assets at year end.	Mohammed & Tamoi (2006) Salama (2017) Garcia – Ayuso & Larrinaga, C. (2003)
Dependent variable			
ER	Environmental Reporting	Total items disclosed divided by maximum (60) items.	Uyagu (2019) Deegan, C., & Blomquist, C. (2006) Toms (2002) Uwuigbe (2011)

Source: Author’s compilation, 2020

4. Results and Discussion

This section presents results and discussion of findings

Table 2
Descriptive Statistics

Variables	Observations	Mean	Std. Dev.	Minimum	Maximum
GD	341	0.124	0.122	0	0.667
FS	341	9.299	2.218	4.230	14.30
ENVI	341	3.90	2.470	1.700	18
ES	341	3.826	1.910	0	21
CD	341	2.791	1.844	0	10

Source: STATA 16

Table 2 shows that gender diversity of the selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria maintains a mean value of 0.124, standard deviation of 0.122, minimum 0 and maximum 0.66% respectively. This means, on the average, 12.4 is the proportion of female on board, while the minimum proportion level is 0. The maximum level of proportion of female on board is 0.667. But the dispersion is due to the difference in number of female members of the selected manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

The firm size has mean of 9.299, standard deviation of 2.218, minimum 4.230 and maximum 14.30 respectively. The environmental information has a mean of 3.952, standard deviation of 2.218, minimum of 1.700 and maximum of 18. This means, on the average, 3.952 of environmental information was declared; while the minimum level declared was 1.700 and the maximum level declared was 18. In like manner, the mean value of employees and safety information is 3.826, standard deviation of 1.910, minimum value of 0 and maximum value of 21. Finally, community development has a mean value of 2.791, standard deviation of 1.844, minimum value of 0 and maximum value of 10.

Normality test was performed, it shows that the data are normally distributed, because the p-values are insignificant at 5% for the variables. Multicollinearity test also shows that the variables are not suffering from multicollinearity since the tolerance values are higher than 0.10 while all the VIF are less than 10. Heteroskedasticity test shows that there is no evidence for the existence of heteroskedasticity while, Hausman specification test shows that random effect will be run on the models.

Table 3
Regression Result

Model 1 (ENVI) Random Effect				Model 2 (ESI) Random Effect			Model 3 (CD) Random Effect		
Variables	Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Coefficients	t-value	p-value	Coefficient	t-value	p-value
Constant	4.073	4.33	0	4.118	5.18	0.008	3.811	5.75	0.007
GD	0.747	-0.89	0.033	0.513	-0.58	0.000	0.481	0.83	0
FS	0.305	-0.05	0.002	0.024	-0.29		0.116	-1.78	0.007
R ²	0.603			0.540			0.509		0.005
W-chi ²	34.045			0.593			3.339		
P-value			0.0006			0.0081			0.008

Source: STATA 16 Outputs

The regression result for model 1 as shown in Table 3 revealed that the relationship between environmental information and gender diversity is a positive relationship, also the relationship between environmental information and firm size shows a positive sign. This simply implies that a 1% increase in gender diversity would result in 0.747% increase in information that will be given out to the public. Similarly, a 1% change in firm size will result in 0.305% increase in information that will be given out to the public.

The relationship between the firm size and information giving out and the relationship between the gender diversity and environmental information shows that both variables are statistically significant in explaining the nature of the information given out, that is both gender diversity and firm size are both statistically significant in influencing the kind of information that is released by the companies. This is supported by the probability value of 0.033 for gender diversity and 0.002 for firm size, this shows that both variables are statistically significant in explaining what happened to the information given out. Also, the model is well specified as this can be seen by the value of R-squared which shows that about 60% changes in the information given out by the companies can be explained by both firm size and gender diversity. In addition, the value of the w-chi² shows that the model is well specified. This is supported by the p-value of 0.0006 which is less than confident level 5%.

The regression result for model two shows that both gender diversity and firm size have positive relationship with employee and safety information. The model shows that the 1% increase in gender diversity will result in employee and safety information increasing by 51% all things being equal, similarly a 1% increase in firm size will lead to 0.24% increase in employee and safety information. This simply means that as the firm increases in size and there is diversity in the board both in number and expertise, the employee safety and information will increase. The model shows that both variables are statistically significant at 95% confidence level. This is supported by p-value of 0.008 for gender diversity and 0.000 for firm size; which are less than 5% level of significance. The R-squared shows that 54% of the information from employee safety and information is explained by both gender diversity and firm size.

The regression result for model three as shown in Table 3 revealed that both gender diversity and firm size have positive impact on community development. Gender diversity with a coefficient of 0.48 simply means that a 1% increase in gender diversity will result in 48% increase in community development, similarly size with a coefficient of 0.116 shows that a 1% increase or decrease in firm size will lead to 12% increase or decrease in community development, all things being equal. The result simply shows that community development is impacted upon by gender diversity and firm size, which means, to increase community development, gender diversity and the size of the firm should be increased. The model shows that the p-value of gender diversity of 0.007 and firm size of 0.0005 which are less than 5% level of significance are statistically significant. The overall model specification shows that the model is well specified, this can be seen from the p-value of 0.008 and R² of 0.51. This means both gender diversity and firm size accounts for 51% changes in community development both in the short-term and long-term according to the model output in relation to competition within the firm among genders and the profitability brought about by the size of a company.

From the analysis of the regression results it can be seen that all the three variables that proxied the dependent variable are positively impacted by the independent variable (gender

diversity) and control variable (firm size). Therefore, it goes to say that gender diversity and firm size have positive significant impact on the overall activities of the firm. The finding agrees with Barako and Brown (2008); Ismail and Ibrahim (2008); Victor and Fodio (2012) who found a positive and significant effect of gender diversity and firm size on environmental reporting. However, the finding disagrees with Liao, Luo and Tang 2014 and Uyagu (2019) who found a positive and insignificant effect of gender diversity and firm size on environmental reporting. In view of the findings, the null hypothesis that says gender diversity has no significant effect on environmental reporting will be rejected, while the alternate will be accepted.

The findings confirm the agency theory that seeks to ameliorate the conflict of interest between the principal and the agents, which if curtailed, can facilitate the significant effect of gender diversity on environmental reporting. The policy implication is that, the management policy of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria with respect to environmental reporting will move toward the direction of increasing the proportion of female directors on board.

5. Conclusion

The study ascertains the significance of gender diversity on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It concludes that gender diversity has positive significant effect on environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This means that the presence of female directors on board can positively increase the level of environmental reporting of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. Consequent upon this finding, it is recommended that, the proportion of female directors on board should be increased in order to create room for improvement in reporting environmental activities in listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. In addition, the Financial Reporting Council of Nigeria (FRCN) should no longer allow environmental reporting to be voluntary, but make it mandatory using ISO 14031 guidelines as a common standard of reporting among the management of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

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